

Condensation of Ethyl Propylacetoacetate with Aromatic Amines. Part II.

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The work described in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 681) has now been extended to α - and β -naphthylamines, *o*-phenetidine, *m*- and *p*-aminophenols, *m*- and *p*-nitroanilines and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloroanilines.

Except with *m*-aminophenol, substituted carbamides $\text{CO}(\text{NHR})_2$ are obtained in addition to the simple anilide $\text{CH}_3\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHR})$; but with α -naphthylamine the amide cannot be isolated. The carbamides are always formed and the yield increases with the time of heating the reaction mixture.

The constitution of the carbamide derivatives was confirmed by preparing them according to the method of Mistry and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 793) by boiling urea with the corresponding amine in amyl alcoholic solution and finding the mixed melting points, when no lowering was observed.

The constitution of the carbamides from α -naphthylamine, *o*-phenetidine, *m*- and *p*-nitroanilines and *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-chloroanilines was further confirmed by heating the compounds with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate when the corresponding acetyl derivatives were obtained. The mixed melting points with specimens prepared from the amines and acetic anhydride showed no lowering; *p*-aminophenol gave the diacetyl derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Di- α -naphthylcarbamide.—A mixture of α -naphthylamine (4 g.) and ethyl propylacetoacetate (5 g.) was boiled for about 10 minutes. The solid separating on cooling was washed with benzene and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in white needles, m. p. 296°. (Found: N, 8.77. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{ON}_2$ requires N, 8.97 per cent).

The melting point of *aa'*-dinaphthylcarbamide, described in literature, is indefinite.*

* It melts at 270° (Delbos, *Annalen*, 1847, 64, 370; Zinnin, *ibid.*, 1859, 108, 229; Pegliani, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 385; Huhn, *Ber.*, 1885, 19, 2405). at 284-86° (Young and Clark, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, 71, 1201), at 314-15° (Vittenet, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1874, ii, 21, 950), at 295-96° (Walther and Wldkowski, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1898, 69, 278; Guha and Saletore, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 574; Mistry and Guha, *loc. cit.*)

Di-β-naphthylcarbamide.—It was prepared and crystallised in the same way as the α- compound, m. p. 310°.† (Found : N, 8·66. $C_{21}H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 8·97 per cent).

n-Propylacetoacet-β-naphthylamide.—The benzene filtrate from di-β-naphthylcarbamide preparation was evaporated, the solid washed with petroleum ether and repeatedly crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 115-16° (Found : N, 5·52. $C_{17}H_{19}O_2N$ requires N, 5·20 per cent).

The same procedure was followed in subsequent preparations, the ester and the respective amine being taken in molecular proportions. The carbamide derivatives, being insoluble in benzene, could be separated from the soluble anilides.

o-Diethoxydiphenylcarbamide, obtained from *o*-phenetidine and the ester, was crystallised from boiling glacial acetic acid in white needles, m. p. 220-21°. (Found : N, 9·68. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9·33 per cent). Migliacci and Gargiulo (*Gazzetta*, 1928, 58, 110) records the melting point as 222°.

n-Propylacetoacet-o-phenetidide.—The benzene filtrate from the above experiment was evaporated and the residue was washed with petroleum ether. It is soluble in ethyl alcohol and dilute acetic acid. It crystallised from methyl alcohol in white needles, m.p. 90-91°. (Found : N, 5·6. $C_{15}H_{21}O_3N$ requires N, 5·32 per cent).

p-Dihydroxydiphenylcarbamide, obtained from *p*-aminophenol and the ester, was triturated with dilute hydrochloric acid to remove the unacted phenol and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. It shrinks at 270° and melts at 280°(decomp.). Struve and Radenhousen (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1895, ii, 52, 238) record its m. p. 230°, and Mistry and Guha (*loc. cit.*), 288° (decomp.). (Found : N, 11·5. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 11·48 per cent).

n-Propylacetoacet-p-hydroxyphenylamide.—The filtrate from the above experiment on evaporation, gave a thick oily liquid with some solid. The oil was drained off and the solid was dried on a porous plate for several days. It is very soluble in almost all organic solvents. It was finally crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 95-96°. (Found : N, 6·33. $C_{13}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 5·96 per cent).

n-Propylacetoacet m-hydroxyphenylamide.—*m*-Aminophenol (5 g.) and the ester (8 g.) were refluxed for about 1 hour. On cooling the liquid became a thick paste from which solid separated on treating

† The melting point of ββ-dinaphthylurea is recorded as 293° (Hubn, *loc. cit.*); 300° (Walther and Wldkowski, *loc. cit.*); 289·90° (Young, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1899, 60, 256); 309·10° (Vittenet, *loc. cit.*; Guha and Saletore, *loc. cit.*; Mistry and Guha, *loc. cit.*) and 286° (Ekstrand, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1360).

with a mixture of benzene and little ether. It was first washed with benzene and finally with dilute hydrochloric acid to remove the unacted phenol and finally crystallised from dilute acetic acid (1:1) in needles, m. p. 223-24°. (Found: N, 6.28. $C_{13}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 5.96 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles. It shrinks at 150° and completely melts at 165°. (Found: N, 5.39. $C_{15}H_{19}O_4N$ requires N, 5.05 per cent).

o-Dichlorodiphenylcarbamide, obtained from *o*-chloroaniline and the ester was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless needles, m. p. 235-36°. It is soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohols and acetic acid, insoluble in benzene, ether, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and petroleum ether. (Found: N, 9.68; Cl, 25.54. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2Cl_2$ requires N, 9.97; Cl, 25.27 per cent). Vittenet (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1899, *iii*, 21, 303) gives the m. p. 235-36° and Manuelli and Rosellini (*Gazzetta*, 1899, 29, *ii*, 128) 238°.

n-Propylacetoacet-*o*-chloroanilide.—The filtrate from the above experiment was evaporated, the residue washed with petroleum ether and crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m. p. 83-84°. It is easily soluble in most of the common organic solvents. (Found: N, 5.32; Cl, 13.59. $C_{13}H_{16}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.52; Cl, 14.0 per cent).

The same compound was obtained by heating the reaction mixture at 140-50° for about 10 hours.

m-Dichlorodiphenylcarbamide was prepared in the same way as its *ortho* isomer and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless needles, m. p. 245.46°.* It resembles the *ortho* compound in its solubility. (Found: N, 9.68; Cl, 25.35. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2Cl_2$ requires N, 9.97; Cl, 25.27 per cent).

n-Propylacetoacet-*m*-chloroanilide was isolated from the benzene filtrate as in the case of its *ortho* isomer and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 88-89°. It resembles the *ortho* compound in solubility. (Found: N, 5.80; Cl, 13.89. $C_{13}H_{16}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.52; Cl, 14.0 per cent). It can also be prepared by heating the reaction mixture at 140-50° for about 6 hours.

p-Dichlorodiphenylcarbamide was prepared in the same way as the *ortho* isomers but heating was required for only 45 minutes. It

* It melts at 245° (Vittenet, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1899, *iii*, 21, 302), at 243°. (Manuelli and Rosellini, *loc. cit.*; Struve and Radenhausen, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1901, 64, *ii*, 332).

crystallised from glacial acetic acid in white needles, m. p. 289-90°.* (Found: N, 9.72; Cl, 24.97. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2Cl_2$ requires N, 9.97 Cl, 25.27 per cent).

n-Propylacetoacet-*p*-chloroanilide was obtained from the benzene filtrate like its isomers and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 123-24°. (Found: N, 5.70; Cl, 13.72. $C_{13}H_{16}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.52; Cl, 14.0 per cent). It can be prepared by heating the reaction mixture at 140-50° for 6 hours.

m-Dinitrodiphenylcarbamide obtained from *m*-nitroaniline and the ester was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in straw-yellow needles, m. p. 241-42°.† (Found: N, 18.75. $C_{13}H_{10}O_5N_4$ requires N, 18.55 per cent).

n-Propylacetoacet-*m*-nitroanilide.—The filtrate from the above experiment on evaporation gave a solid which was first washed with petroleum ether and then with dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m. p. 95-96°. (Found: N, 10.51. $C_{13}H_{16}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10.61 per cent). The compound can be obtained by heating the reaction mixture at 170-80° for 4 hours.

p-Dinitrodiphenylcarbamide was prepared in the same way as its *meta* isomer, m. p. 310°.‡ (Found: N, 18.71. $C_{13}H_{10}O_5N_4$ requires N, 18.55 per cent).

n-Propylacetoacet-*p*-nitroanilide was obtained from the benzene filtrate in the same way as its *meta* isomer and crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 118-19°. (Found: N, 10.64. $C_{13}H_{16}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10.61 per cent).

* It melts at 270° (Beilstein and Kurbatow, *Annalen*, 1875, 176, 51), at 306.07° (Vittenet, *loc. cit.*), at 275° (Manuelli and Rosellini, *loc. cit.*), at 310° (Chattaway and Orton *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 1075; Bamberger and Destraz, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1878), at 270° (Bougault and Leboncq, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1930, *iv*, 47, 594).

† It melts at 233° (Losanitsch, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 50), at 229° (Struve and Radenhausen, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1895, *ii*, 52, 213), at 225° Vittenet, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1899, *iii*, 21, 156; Offret, *ibid.*, p. 778; Manuelli and Rosellini (*loc. cit.*), at 233° (Loh and Dehn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 2956).

‡ The melting point of this compound has been recorded as 312° (Struve and Radenhausen, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1895, *ii*, 52, 238; Manuelli and Rosellini, *loc. cit.*) and 310° (Vittenet, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1899, *iii*, 21, 149; Mistry and Guha, *loc. cit.*).